

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE INTRODUCTION OF THE NECESSARY PRODUCTS INTO THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS TO EQUIP THE STEAM LAB

Dossymov Y.,

PhD., Khoja Akhmet Yassawi International Kazakh-Turkish University, Kazakhstan

Ramankulov Sh.,

PhD., Khoja Akhmet Yassawi International Kazakh-Turkish University, Kazakhstan

Akhanova A.,

PhD-student., Khoja Akhmet Yassawi International Kazakh-Turkish University, Kazakhstan

Berdi D.,

PhD., Khoja Akhmet Yassawi International Kazakh-Turkish University, Kazakhstan

Rizakhojayeva G.

PhD., Khoja Akhmet Yassawi International Kazakh-Turkish University, Kazakhstan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13285629>

Abstract

This article discusses the issues of evaluating the effectiveness in the educational process of products aimed at developing the training of future physicists in English, developed in the STEAM laboratory. Monograph «Improving the methodology of teaching the discipline «Electricity and magnetism» based on STEAM technology», computer software «Mobile App Physics – 1» and «Physics eBook-I» (Based on STEAM+CLIL)», textbook «STEM education: putting knowledge into practice» introduced in the educational process in some universities and secondary schools of the Republic of Kazakhstan. STEAM products used in teaching the courses «Physics», «Technique of physical experiment at school», «Electricity and Magnetism», «Mechanics», «Molecular physics», «Optics», «Alternative energy sources», «STEAM in alternative energy projects: solar energy» positively contributed to improving the training of students in English. The effectiveness of the pedagogical experiment was demonstrated by the indicators of creativity of students in engineering and technical fields, as well as the development of indicators of scientific research competence. «This research has been/was/is funded by the Science Committee of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan (Grant No. AP14870844)».

Keywords: *STEAM education, future physics teachers, English, teaching process, technical and engineering training*

Introduction

The engineering and technical field is a wide-ranging discipline that focuses on the application of scientific advances and technological innovations in life. This industry makes a great contribution to meeting the various needs of society and ensuring economic development. Engineering and technical innovations increase production efficiency and ensure economic growth. Engineering and technical professions create new jobs and make a huge contribution to the economy. Engineers create new technologies and products, paving the way for innovation. This process combines scientific principles with specific applied research to create ways to gain new knowledge [1]. Physics can be attributed to one of the engineering and technical disciplines. Therefore, one of the most pressing issues is the development of the methodological system of teaching physics in accordance with modern requirements.

The STEM CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) Project aims to develop subject content and language skills in parallel by combining science, technology, engineering and mathematics in teaching physics. The features of teaching physics in English include several aspects, including language and subject integration, mastery of terminology, intercultural contacts, and innovation in teaching methods [2].

The scientific terminology of physics is complex and requires special knowledge. In the process of teaching physics in English, it is important for students to master special terminology. English is the international language of science, so teaching physics in English strengthens intercultural ties. Teaching physics in English requires the use of innovative learning methods. This increases students' interest in the subject and makes the learning process more effective.

However, in the process of introducing these technologies, a number of problems arise. The equipment and resources needed to equip STEM laboratories [3] and implement the CLIL methodology can be expensive. For example, robotics kits, sensors, 3D printers and interactive whiteboards require significant funds. Teachers may not have the necessary skills and knowledge in STEM and CLIL methods. Adding STEM and CLIL elements to your training program may require additional time. It is difficult to allocate enough time for the development of theoretical and practical skills of students. Financial support, teacher training, curriculum development, technical support, and language support for students are important to address these problems. Through the implementation of these measures, STEM and CLIL technologies can be effectively used in the teaching of physics.

As a solution to these scientific problems, in our research we aim to contribute to the comprehensive development and future success of students by creating English-language products in STEAM laboratories. These laboratories allow you to apply theoretical knowledge in practice, develop creative and critical thinking skills, master technical skills, and improve teamwork skills.

The main part

Research methods focused on STEAM and CLIL technologies allow the comprehensive development of students, the simultaneous development of their subject and language skills. These methods make the learning process more efficient, interesting and interactive.

As a result of our research STEAM equipment models have been developed and printed on a 3D printer in computer programs for the subjects "Alternative Energy Sources", "Electricity and Magnetism". Educational and laboratory stands have been developed aimed at studying the physical characteristics of wind and solar energy. These stands allow you to perform about 20 laboratory work, depending on the physical characteristics of solar and wind energy. The content of laboratory work performed on demonstration equipment was prepared and integrated into the educational process. In connection with the methodology of using these stands and demonstration equipment in the educational process, a textbook "STEM education: putting knowledge into practice" was developed and printed. The mobile application "Mobile App Mobile App Physics-1" has been developed, an author's certificate for the electronic textbook "Physics eBook – I" (Based on STEAM+CLIL) has been obtained".

For use in the educational process, the mobile application "mobile application Physics-1" has been developed. This application covers several physics topics. Let's focus on the structure of the mobile application. The mobile application consists of several structural elements: theoretical data, test kits, video lectures. In the section theoretical data, theoretical data on general physics is presented in English. Also, after the theoretical information, the "dictionary" contains terms related to the same topic in Russian and Kazakh. The electronic tool "Physics eBook – I" (Based on STEAM+CLIL) " consists of a Content section collected in theoretical data. This section covers 14 physics topics. In order to test students' knowledge, test tasks are placed on the left panel in the TEST TASKS section [4-5].

By clicking on the button called Laboratory, it enters the window where the laboratory works are located. The electronic manual includes Determination of the acceleration of a body moving along an inclusive trough, Study of the dependence of the flight distance of the body on the throwing angle, Determination of equilibrium conditions of the lever, Determination of the efficiency of the inclusive plane, Let's determine the acceleration of free fall using a pendulum, Study of elastic deformations, study of sliding friction force, measurement of sliding friction Cooperative, Study of Archimedes'law, determination of the conditions of the body floating in liquid, 11 laboratory works on Determination of density of solids and liquids are presented. In the left part of the window, theoretical data related to the topic is presented, and in the right part, a window for performing laboratory work opens, which allows you to perform it interactively. Theoretical data on laboratory work are presented in English (Figure 1).

Figure 1. «Mobile App Physics -1» and «Physics eBook – I «(Based on STEAM+CLIL)» programs for the computer

The STEAM + CLIL education system contributes to the comprehensive development of students, increasing their creative and innovative abilities, as well as becoming competitive at the global level by mastering a foreign language.

The bilingual manual "STEM education: putting knowledge into practice" is intended for students to master STEM knowledge on the example of teaching the discipline "optics". In addition to theoretical knowledge, each section contains practical STEM tasks, control questions, tests, level reports, and projects. The manual is divided into 8 sections in order to master the basic concepts of the discipline "optics":

1) Light phenomena. Propagation of light in a straight line. Light values;

2) Fundamentals of Beam optics. Reflection and refraction of light on a flat surface. The phenomenon of full internal reflection;

3) Lenses. Image output in the lens. Image in a flat mirror;

4) Light interference. Coherent waves. Interferometers;

5) Diffraction of light. Diffraction brushes. Polarization of light;

6) Polarization of light at reflection and refraction. Rotation of the polarization plane;

7) Dispersion of light. Absorption and scattering of light, mutual influence of light and matter;

8) Effects of light. Photoelectric effect. Compton effect. Light pressure. This manual has a number of features in mastering the results of training.

9) The manual consists of several parts: - theoretical part; - STEM activity tasks; - STEM and creative tasks.

The bilingual manual "STEM education: putting knowledge into practice" is intended for students studying physics, pedagogy and Natural Sciences in higher educational institutions. It helps teachers and students to optimize the learning process and develop STEM projects.

For this reason, their desire to use more modeling allowed us to launch the content of the "Design, Modeling & Smart Digital Labs" website in a thorough way

(<https://sites.google.com/view/steamclil>). The site was loaded with materials developed in order to develop the movement of graduates towards new knowledge by expanding the approach to the Steam approach in education. Materials were developed and uploaded to the site, which will help students and teachers, school teachers to master the STEAM industry in English. In addition, the site included digital laboratories, educational and methodological complex in disciplines, information on the content of laboratory work and facilities (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Main page of the training portal.

The section "Laboratory" shows Training stands in the STEM Laboratory, in particular equipment based on wind energy and solar energy. In addition, the characteristics of laboratory work related to solar energy10

are given. Finally, scientific articles published within the framework of the grant project are included (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Main page of the training portal.

The course offered in alternative energy sources is aimed at the solar energy sector, including. This topic is of high relevance due to the fact that we consider it as a solution to global problems at the global level. The general content, purpose and lectures of the course can be viewed in the section "course program and content". If we click on the "content of Alternative Energy Sources" button, we get access to the syllabus of the discipline, the complex, laboratory work and media

files. The next section presents events, seminars, competitions held within the framework of the project. The "laboratory" section shows the facilities in the STEM laboratory.

Based on the results of control work at the beginning and end of academic disciplines.

As for the results of the obtained values before the experiment (table 1), they were divided into three levels-low, medium and high, and their standard deviation with an average value was calculated.

Table 1.

Results of the obtained values before the experiment

Category	Control group		Experiment group	
	M	SD	M	SD
Low	4,15	1,558	4,058	1,3047
Middle	7	0	7,4	0,489
High	9	0,816	9,5	0,5

It was observed that the levels of students after the experiment increased significantly compared to their previous levels before the experiment was conducted. Their results are shown in the table below (table 2).

Table 1.

Results of the obtained values after the experiment

Category	Control group		Experiment group	
	M	SD	M	SD
Low group	4,67	1,25	5,25	0,433
Middle group	7,5	0,25	7,6	0,493
High group	9	0	9,3	0,471

Figure 4. Difference between the control group and the experimental group

With the diagram shown above, it is possible to observe the difference between the control group and the experimental group (Figure 4). In the study, which was collected from 50 students, the researchers measured the skills of creating hypotheses, compiling experiments, collecting data. The results of the experiment before and after the period were correlated and measured their statistical significance by calculating the t test.

Table 2.

Result of the level of students before the experiment

Group (Before)	n	X	Sd	df	t	p
CG	26	5,038	2,19	48	-0,275	0,7845
EG	24	5,208	2,18			

Table 2 shows the result of the level of students before the experiment. Shows that there is no significant difference between the control group and the experiment group.

Table 3.

Result of the level of students after the experiment

Group (After)	n	X	Sd	df	t	p
BT	26	5,23	1,716	48	-4,01	0,0002
ET	24	7	1,44			

The above table, the statistical results of the obtained students after the experiment. There was a significant difference between the post-experimental, control and experimental groups in terms of student levels: $t(48) = -4.01$, $P < .0002$. The result of this study was determined by the researchers using a statistical test. A statistical test is a mathematical operation used to test

hypotheses using statistical methods. If we fully focus on the calculated statistical test: we calculate whether the average values of the two groups are statistically significant using the t test.

Thanks to the conduct of such a statistical test, it is possible not only to find out the statistical signifi-

cance between the levels of students, but also to combine their methods of teaching a foreign language, which shows that in the multilingual world, the STEAM CLIL model is relevant.

Conclusion

The results of the study will allow us to develop a methodology for teaching engineering and technical disciplines, including physics, in English using the STEAM approach. Based on several STEAM fairs organized in urban and rural schools, it helps to reduce the gap in pedagogical processes. It helps to increase the number of qualified teachers who are able to repair or fake faulty equipment. STEAM contributes to the development of the science and technology industry in our country by training future teachers who can effectively convey the necessary knowledge in the engineering and technical field to students in English. Demonstration tools developed in the course of the study, a set of equipment for performing subprojects necessary for the Steam cabinet, digital educational resources influenced the high level of English proficiency of future physics teachers through their integration into the educational process. Increased the potential for commercialization, having a positive impact on the fulfillment of socio-economic requirements.

Acknowledgments

«This research has been/was/is funded by the Science Committee of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan (Grant No. AP14870844)».

References:

1. Wuchty S, Jones B, Uzzi B. (2007). The increasing dominance of teams in the production of knowledge. *Science* 316:1036–1039.
2. Johnson, H. (2021). A STEM CLIL Pilot Project in Ecuadorian High Schools. In 6th International STEM Education Conference, iSTEM-Ed 2021. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1109/iSTEM-Ed52129.2021.9625068>
3. Tytler, R. (2020). STEM Education for the Twenty-First Century (pp. 21–43). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-52229-2_3
4. K. Kelesbayev, Ramankulov., Dosymov E., Asanbek B. Mobile App Physics -1. Author's Certificate No.38170, July 28, 2023.
5. Usembayeva I., Kurbanbekov B., Rakhmankulov Sh., Edilbayev E. program for the computer "Physics eBook – I "(Based on STEAM+CLIL)". Author's Certificate No.38314, August 9, 2023.
6. Sh.Ramankulov, M.Nurizanova, Y.Dosymov, A.Akhanova. Principles and content of teaching physics in english for future physics teachers. The Bulletin the National Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Kazakhstan, Volume 3. Number 403 (2023), 172-186. <https://doi.org/10.32014/2023.2518-1467.501>